

DEVELOPMENT OF PADDY TURNING ATTACHMENT FOR POWER TILLER

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Abstract:

Mechanization plays very important role in reducing the cost of cultivation of any crop. Though rice crop is equipped with mechanization for all its field operations, its use is limited because of high cost of machinery. Drying is one of the important field operations in paddy cultivation, where the farmers mostly practice open sun drying in drying yards. Turning of paddy in drying yards is done by manual labour which is very arduous and need a mechanical solution to turn the paddy at every 30 minutes under hot sun. Hence, a paddy turning attachment was developed to fit to the power tiller, which is already existing with the farmers. the drying rate of the machine turned paddy was observed same as the manually turned paddy. In 11 hours of time the moisture content of the paddy was reduced from 19.42 % to 13.28% and 13.02 % respectively in machine turned paddy and manually turned paddy. the drying rate was observed uniform in both methods in constant rate period and was observed more in manually turned paddy compared to machine turned paddy in falling rate period. This is due to the formation of ridges and furrows in manually turned paddy compared to machine turned paddy. Hence, it is inferred that, the paddy turning attachment should be provided with rake kind of structure on back side of it, to make ridge and furrows after turning the paddy with belt paddles.

Keywords: Drying of paddy, turning attachment, open sun drying, moisture content (%wb)

Introduction:

Rice is one of the widely cultivated crops which requires mechanization in every field operation. Though rice crop is fully mechanized, simple and low-cost machinery is a setback in rice cultivation. High initial cost, lack of repair facilities, less access to spare parts, need of expertise for operating machinery are some of the problems with foreign made machinery. Hence development of low cost and local made machinery are highly essential for small and marginal farms of our country. Drying is one of the important field operations of paddy cultivation. Late and improper drying results in formation of molds and insects which will reduce the milling quality and storage life of the rice. Freshly harvested paddy typically has a high moisture content of 20–26% wet basis. To ensure paddy rice has consistent quality and a longer duration of storage life, it must be dried to moisture content of 14% or lower before storage (Ying et al. 2024). The moisture in the harvested paddy exists in two areas. the surface and the inner core of the rice kernel. Drying technologies are generally optimized to manage drying in both areas while minimizing the negative impact of paddy drying (Dong et al., 2009). During the paddy drying process, the moisture removal rate varies depending on the location of the moisture in the kernel (Akhtaruzzaman et al., 2022, Mossman, A.P et al. 1986). Though some of the driers are available in the market none of them are economically viable except in adverse climatic conditions. Hence sun drying is most economical and feasible way to dry the produce from harvesting moisture content (18-21%) to storage moisture content (13-14%).

Sun drying is a cumbersome process as the person should walk in field in hot summer for every half an hour for proper mixing or turning of grains upside down to achieve uniform drying. Therefore, development of machinery for turning of paddy grains in drying yards is very much essential to reduce the drudgery involved and labour dependency. A paddy turning device is a tool used to manually turn and spread paddy (unhusked rice) during the drying process in open yards. This helps ensure even drying by exposing all grains to sunlight and air. The paddy turning attachment to the powertiller does the same operation as the paddy turning device.

Proper mixing of grains is important during the sun drying process, as the improper drying results in low head rice recovery and re-adsorption

of moisture to the dried grains. As recommended by Post Harvest Unit of IRRI for proper drying of grains, the optimum thickness of grain layer is 2–4 cm and for every 30 minutes the grains should be turned upside down. Manually mixing or turning of grains for every thirty minutes requires lot of labour and drudgery involved in turning of paddy in hot sun deters labour from taking up the job. This project was taken up to address the problem of unavailability of labour and drudgery involved in turning of paddy in drying yards.

Review of literature:

Aman et al. 2019, investigated the drying loss of paddy both in traditional sun drying and mechanized drying method (BAU-STR dryer). The results showed that the average drying loss of paddy in BAU-STR dryer was found 0.48% and 0.36% during Boro and Aman seasons, respectively at 2015 and 2016 while sun drying loss at farmer's field level was found 3.95, 3.24, 2.98 2.41 and 3.04%. The low cost BAU-STR dryer would be an alternative and effective drying technology to save 1.4 MMT of paddy by reducing 2.7% losses of national production (51.87 MMT). Imoudu et al. 2000, studied the effects of sun-drying on milling and the quality of rice (*Oryza*) in terms of milling yield and percentage of broken grains. Samples of each were then sun-dried on a concrete floor or on a mat and were milled at different levels of moisture content. They inferred that, the parboiled rice dried on a concrete floor gave a higher yield percentage and a lower proportion of broken grains than did grains dried on a mat. Narmilan et al. 2021, evaluated the suitability and effectiveness of the drying pad and thickness as practiced by local paddy farmers during the sun drying process. It was found that the duration of drying of paddy from 28% to 13% moisture content on a dry basis was 300 to 540 minutes depending upon the drying pad and thickness. The tarpaulin is reasonable at shallow thickness with less time to reach the necessary moisture level than other drying pads.

Materials & Methods:**Development of paddy turning attachment:**

A 13 hp VST Shakti power tiller was taken for the study. Power tiller tines are replaced with the belt paddles as shown in the figure 3.1 (a) to turn the paddy grains on threshing floor. Total 18 no. of belt paddles were fitted to the powertiller by removing the blades. The fitted belt paddles are shown in the Fig. 3.1 (b).

(a)

(b)

Fig.3.1. (a) Belt blades (b) Belt blades fitted to powertiller

Performance evaluation of paddy turning attachment:

Performance evaluation of the paddy turning attachment was done at Regional Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru. Paddy grains at 19.42 % (wb) moisture content were spread on the threshing floor in two batches in an area of 4.5 m x 4.5 m each. One batch of grains were turned with developed paddy turning attachment (Fig. 12.3) and other batch of grains were turned manually (Fig. 12.2) for every one hour. The moisture content of the grains at every one hour was recorded. The weather conditions at the time of experiment are given in table 2.1.

Plate 12.2. Manually turned paddy

Plate 12.3. Machine turned paddy

Fig. 12.4. Moisture meter for measuring Moisture content of paddy

Table 2.1.: Weather conditions at the time of drying

Date	Max. Temperature	Min. Temperature	RH1 (8AM)	RH2 (2 PM)
22-12-2024	27 °C	19 °C	92.6 %	70.8 %
23-12-2024	27 °C	19 °C	90.7%	44.1%
24-12-2024	27 °C	19 °C	77.7%	47.4%

The paddy grains were further tested for its germination percentage. A total of 10 samples were taken from each batch to conduct the germination test for 100 grains. Germination test was conducted in physiology lab of RARS, Maruteru. Dickey John moisture meter was used to measure the moisture content of paddy (Fig.12.4). The germination percentage was calculated by using the following equation.

$$\text{Germination (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of seeds germinated}}{\text{No. of seeds planted}} \times 100$$

Results and Discussion:

The moisture content (% wb) of paddy turned in both methods were measured using moisture meter. The moisture contents were measured for every one hour and are presented in table 12.1. The moisture contents show that, total 17 hours were required for reducing the moisture content of the paddy from 19.42 % to 11%. Up to 9 hours of drying, the drying rate was same in both machine turned paddy and manually turned paddy. After 9 th hour of drying in open sun, the drying rate was observed more in manually turned paddy compared to machine turned paddy (Fig.). This behavior may be due to formation of ridges and furrows in manually turned paddy where in more exposed area to the sun contributed to the

faster drying. Where as in machine turned paddy, belt paddles turn the paddy in sheet form, and there are no ridges and furrows formed, which made the drying rate slower. Ying et al., 2024 indicated that, the surface moisture generally evaporates faster. In contrast, removing moisture from the core of the kernel requires the right balance of heat for moisture to migrate from the core to the outer surface, which may take longer than drying surface moisture. Thus, paddy drying is characterized by three phases: the preheating period where the paddy begins to absorb heat but expresses only a slight moisture change; the constant-rate period, where the surface of the paddy reaches a steady temperature and continuous water evaporation; and the falling-rate period, which represents the time for internal water to migrate to the surface and evaporate at a declining rate, usually occurring when the moisture content(%wb) of paddy is below 18% MC. The similar trend was observed in this study i.e up to 9 hours of drying (constant rate period) the drying rate was uniform in both the methods of turning and after 9th hour the drying (falling rate period) rate was more in manually turned paddy compared to machine turned paddy.

Table.4.1. Moisture content of paddy grains at different hours of drying

S.No.	Drying hours	Moisture content (% wb) of paddy in Manual turning of paddy	Moisture content (% wb) of paddy in Machine turning of paddy
1	0	19.42	19.42
2	1	18.58	18.40
3	2	18.06	17.94
4	3	17.46	17.18
5	4	16.70	16.46
6	5	16.40	16.26
7	6	16.22	16.00
8	7	15.80	15.50
9	8	15.50	14.90
10	9	14.72	14.52
11	10	13.46	14.26
12	11	13.02	13.28
13	12	12.48	13.06
14	13	12.18	12.64
15	14	12.00	12.60
16	15	11.42	12.48
17	16	11.14	12.12
18	17	10.42	11.56

Fig. 4.2. Moisture content of paddy grains in different drying times

Germination test showed that, the germination percentage of machine turned paddy was observed as 85% and manually turned paddy was observed as 88%.

Conclusion:

The following conclusions were drawn from the study.

1. The drying rate was on par in both manual turning of paddy and machine turning of paddy for first 9 hours of drying.
2. After 9 hours of drying the drying was faster in manual turning of paddy compared to machine turning of paddy this may be due to formation of ridges and furrows which makes more area to expose to sun in manual turning of paddy
3. where as in machine turning of paddy, the grains are turned in the form of sheet, though they are turned upside down well the area exposed to sun is less compared to manual turning of paddy. This made the drying rate lesser in case of machine turning of paddy.
4. Germination (%) of manually and machine turned paddy were observed as 88% and 86% respectively.
5. Hence an attachment which makes ridges and furrows structure on the back of developed attachment for power tiller is necessary to have similar or more drying rate in case of machine turning of paddy

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